

WORKSHOP #1
Seminar on marine litter

Workshop Brief

The first NETTAG+ workshop, entitled ‘Seminar on marine litter’, is an educational seminar targeting small- and large-scale professional fishers to raise awareness of the problem of marine litter, focusing on the adverse environmental and socio-economic effects of marine litter and ALDFG, how fishers can minimise waste and reduce harmful environmental impacts associated with bycatch and ghost fishing. Moreover, this educational seminar will also address the possible use of alternative materials, and strategies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, energy and resource consumption.

The workshop takes approximately one hour and a half (see the proposed agenda) and will address the following themes:

- The importance of the ocean and main threats.
- The problem of marine litter (including plastic and microplastic pollution).
- Contribution of fisheries to marine litter and its adverse environmental and socio-economic impacts (e.g., ALDFG, litter produced on board).
- Other environmental harmful impacts of fisheries (such as bycatch, greenhouse gas emissions).
- European actions to tackle marine litter from sea-based sources.
- Best practices regarding the management of litter, possible use of alternative materials and reduction of emissions and environmental harmful impacts.

The main expected learning outcomes include:

- Understanding marine litter and its effects on marine wildlife, socio-economic activities, and human well-being.
- Gaining insight into other environmental impacts associated with fisheries.
- Introducing participants to best practices to tackle these challenges.

Workshop development

Registration

The registration team welcome the participants and hand them the Participant Information Sheet, two Informed Consent Forms, the NETTAG+ Flyer and the Feedback form. Participants

are asked to sign the presence list and return the signed informed consent form (each participant should keep a copy for themselves).

Welcome and presentation of the NETTAG+ project

| 15 minutes

After the welcome, there will be a quick presentation of the objectives and activities planned for the workshop and a brief presentation of the NETTAG+ project.

Seminar on marine litter

| 60 minutes

The 'Seminar on marine litter' will be presented, using the PowerPoint presentation previously prepared.

Discussion

| 15 minutes

Following the presentation, participants are encouraged to pose questions and engage in a discussion on the seminar topics. Participants are requested to complete the feedback form and to leave it at the registration table.

Resources and materials

Two PowerPoint presentations were prepared, one with a general introduction to the NETTAG+ project and another one with the themes to be addressed and discussed with fishers during the workshop.

Note that the Seminar presentation offers theoretical knowledge intended as a foundation for all subsequent workshops. If partners opt to combine certain workshops in the same event, it's recommended to categorize them by theme and potentially divide the Seminar presentation accordingly. To facilitate this process, the slides corresponding to each workshop have been identified.

WORKSHOP #1
Seminar on marine litter

Resources

1st WORKSHOP

Seminar on marine litter

Agenda

Place | Date | Time

- | | |
|----------------------|---|
| 13:45 - 14:00 | Registration |
| 14:00 - 14:15 | Welcome and presentation of the NETTAG+ project |
| 14:15 - 15:15 | Seminar on Marine Litter |
| 15:15 - 15:30 | Discussion |
| 15:30 - 15:50 | Coffee Break |

Feedback Form

We ask you to take a moment to provide your feedback on the workshop. Your responses will be used to improve future NETTAG+ workshops.

Name (optional): _____

On a scale of 1 to 4 where 1 is strongly disagree and 4 is strongly agree, please circle the most appropriate answer:

1. The Workshop venue was:

- | | | | | |
|--|---|---|---|---|
| a) Comfortable | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Well located | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) Food and refreshments were adequate | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

2. The Workshop content was:

- | | | | | |
|-----------------------|---|---|---|---|
| a) Relevant | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Comprehensive | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) Easy to understand | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

3. The Workshop was:

- | | | | | |
|--|---|---|---|---|
| a) Well paced | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Breaks were sufficient | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) A good mix between listening and activities | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

4. The facilitators were:

- | | | | | |
|--|---|---|---|---|
| a) Knowledgeable | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| b) Well-prepared | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |
| c) Responsive to participant's questions | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 |

5. What did you like best about this Workshop?

6. What did you like least about this Workshop?

Thank you for participating, we appreciate your feedback.

Presentation of the NETTAG+ project

Partner | Date

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program, Grant No. 101112812 (NETTAGPlus).

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA).

Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

www.nettagplus.eu

Follow @NetTagProject

NETTAG+ project

NETTAG+ Preventing, avoiding and mitigating environmental impacts of fishing gear and associated marine litter

- ✓ Funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program
- ✓ Three-year project: 01/05/2023 to 30/04/2026
- ✓ Coordination: CIIMAR – Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research (Portugal)
- ✓ Contributes to the European Commission Mission 'Restore our ocean and waters by 2030'
- ✓ NETTAG+ aims to **upgrade** and **upscale** the integrative preventive approach that started in the previous NetTag project (2019-2021), and to replicate it in Mediterranean regions

NETTAG+ consortium

Multidisciplinary and international team

15 partners from **7 different countries** with a strong academia-industry collaboration

MINISTRY FOR AGRICULTURE, FISHERIES AND ANIMAL RIGHTS
PARLIAMANTARY SECRETARIAT FOR FISHERIES, AQUACULTURE AND ANIMAL RIGHTS

Funded by the European Union

NETTAG+ overview

Based on synergistic activities between the fisheries industry, scientists and NGOs, NETTAG+ is developing three solutions to PREVENT, AVOID and MITIGATE the harmful impacts of fishing gear

PREVENT

Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean

AVOID

Fishing Gear Location with Acoustic Tags

MITIGATE

Detection and Removal of Abandoned, Lost or otherwise Discarded Fishing Gear (ALDFG)

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NETTAG+ objectives

PREVENT

Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean

- ✓ **Empower the fisheries sector**, namely professional fishers, **to adopt more environmental-friendly** fishing methods, **prevent marine litter** and increase responsible user behaviour.
- ✓ **Create adequate conditions** for the reception and treatment of litter **at fishing ports**, including through recycling and reuse.
- ✓ **Recognize and reward the volunteer service** provided by fishers when retrieving marine litter that is passively collected in fishing gear.

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NETTAG+ objectives

AVOID

Fishing Gear Location with Acoustic Tags

- ✓ Develop and engineer **acoustic tags** to be attached to fishing gear as a sustainable, low-cost and innovative low-impact solution to improve mapping, tracking and recovery of lost fishing gear.
- ✓ Improve a **robotic surface system** linked with the acoustic tag system for lost fishing gear location/recovery.

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NETTAG+ objectives

MITIGATE

Detection and Removal of Abandoned, Lost or otherwise Discarded Fishing Gear (ALDFG)

- ✓ Develop a **system to detect ALDFG** in the Ocean water column and seabed.
- ✓ Co-develop, with fishers, a **robotic tool to detect, map, track and recover ALDFG.**

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NETTAG+ demonstrative events

The three NETTAG+ solutions will be **tested, validated and demonstrated in real conditions** in **Atlantic** and **Mediterranean** countries: **Portugal, Spain, Italy, Croatia, Malta** and **United Kingdom**

	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP3	<input type="checkbox"/>
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP4
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP4
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WP2 PREVENT

Fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean

WP3 AVOID

Fishing Gear Location with Acoustic Tags

WP4 MITIGATE

Detection and Removal of ALDFG (Map, Track and Recover)

Thank you

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Seminar on Marine Litter

Participatory Workshop #1

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Indicate the place | indicate the date dd/mm/yyyy

TRANSPORT

the ocean is essential for marine transportation

CLIMATE REGULATION

covering 70% of the Earth's surface, helps to regulate the climate

> 50% O₂

AIR WE BREATHE

produces over half of the world's oxygen

CLIMATE REGULATION

covering 70% of the Earth's surface, helps to regulate the climate

BLUE ECONOMY

several billions euros are generated from the oceans

RECREATION

provides unique activities, such as fishing, surfing, diving,

FOOD

source of seafood, fish and essential ingredients

MEDICINE

many medical products come from the ocean

IMPORTANCE OF OUR OCEAN

Main ocean threats

PLASTIC/MARINE POLLUTION

14 LIFE BELOW WATER

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

1 NO POVERTY	2 ZERO HUNGER	3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING	4 QUALITY EDUCATION	5 GENDER EQUALITY	6 CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION
7 AFFORDABLE AND CLEAN ENERGY	8 DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH	9 INDUSTRY, INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE	10 REDUCED INEQUALITIES	11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES	12 RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION
13 CLIMATE ACTION	14 LIFE BELOW WATER	15 LIFE ON LAND	16 PEACE, JUSTICE AND STRONG INSTITUTIONS	17 PARTNERSHIPS FOR THE GOALS	

UN, 2022: <https://unstats.un.org/sdgs/report/2022/img/info/Goal-14.pdf>

MARINE LITTER

EEA: <https://youtu.be/T7Cb44ab-YI>

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What is marine litter?

“ Any persistent, manufactured or processed solid material discarded, disposed of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment. ”

UNEP (1995)

- deliberately discarded into the sea, rivers or beaches
- brought indirectly to the sea with rivers, sewage, storm water or winds
- accidentally lost, including material lost at sea in bad weather (fishing gear, cargo)
- deliberately left by people on beaches and shores

Where does it come from?

20%
comes from the sea

- Lost shipping containers
- Lost/discharged maritime activities gear (e.g. fisheries, aquaculture, shipping, oil platforms, wind farms)

Ocean is the final destination of litter!

80%
comes from the land

Major causes are poor waste management and littering on land

- Litter dropped in cities, at the beach...
- Industrial waste discharges
- Litter blown by the wind
- Poorly managed landfills
- Microbeads from hygiene products
- Sewage related litter

Based on: EEA, 2023. [From source to sea – The untold story of marine litter](#)

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Where does it go?

A significant amount of the marine litter is located at the sea bottom!

70% of marine litter is in the sea bottom

15% water surface and column

15% beaches and coastal waters

Where does it go?

- Litter items can be transported across the seas and oceans over long distances by currents and gyres and accumulated in offshore 'garbage patch' areas
- The Great Pacific Garbage Patch is the best known
- It covers an estimated surface area of 1.6 million km² (3 times the size of France)

Watch [The Ocean Cleanup](https://theoceancleanup.com/great-pacific-garbage-patch/) video for more info:
[The Great Pacific Garbage Patch Explained](https://theoceancleanup.com/great-pacific-garbage-patch/)

1. North Pacific Gyre
2. Indian Ocean Gyre
3. South Pacific Gyre
4. South Atlantic Gyre
5. North Atlantic Gyre

<https://theoceancleanup.com/great-pacific-garbage-patch/>

What type of litter?

Data source (graph): [European Parliament](#), 2018

85% of land-based litter is plastic

Top 10 single-use plastic items

Addressed by the EU Directive 2019/904 on single-use plastics

Cotton buds

Beverage containers

Cutlery, straws and stirrers

Cigarette butts

Balloons and balloon sticks

Plastic bags

Food containers

Packets and wrappers

Cups for beverages

Wet wipes and sanitary items

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Data source: European Commission, 2018
https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/plastics/single-use-plastics_en

Sources of plastics in the environment

The source

The primary source of marine litter is **mismanagement plastic waste**, which slowly leaks into the environment.

In 2018, it amounted to **3 million tonnes**.

Approximately **80% of marine litter starts on land**, while 20% begins at the sea.

Illegal dumping and unsanitary landfilling

Sources of mismanaged plastic waste

Agriculture

Tourism, consumerism and littering

How plastics spread to the environment?

Adapted from: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/media/infographics/sources-and-pathways-of-plastics/view>

Plastic litter in the sea

PLASTIC LITTER IN THE SEA

GLOBAL EMERGENCY

over 150 million tonnes
PLASTICS

1 tonne PLASTICS ↔ for every 3 tonnes FISH

PLASTICS ↔ more than FISH

WWF (2018). Out of the plastic trap saving the Mediterranean from plastic pollution

Microplastics

What are microplastics and where do they come from?

- Microplastics are tiny pieces of plastic material typically **smaller than 5 mm**
- Originate from degradation of larger plastic objects, such as plastic bags, bottles or fishing nets
- Directly released in the environment as small particles

European Parliament 2018. [Microplastics: sources, effects and solutions](#), accessed Nov. 2023

Based on <https://mp-1.itrcweb.org/environmental-distribution-fate-and-transport/#gsc.tab=0>

Plastics and microplastics

Some numbers in the marine environment

- Plastic waste enters the ocean at a rate of **11 million metric tons per year**
(The Pew Charitable Trusts and SYSTEMIQ, 2020)
- Over **200.000 tonnes** of plastic waste enters the Mediterranean Sea every year - a number that is expected to double if significant measures are not taken
(IUCN, 2020)
- Recent research estimates that at least **14.4 million tonnes of microplastics** have found its way to the bottom of the world's oceans
(Barrett *et al.*, 2020)

Plastics and microplastics

Impacts on the marine environment

Facilitate the spread of diseases or invasive species

Smothering the marine life
(preventing oxygen and nutrient flow and blocking light, reducing the number of organisms)

Entanglement of animals
(birds, fish, turtles and mammals in abandonment fishing gear and plastic packaging)

Microplastics **affect species living in bottom** environments and cause **ecosystem disruption**

Ingestion of plastic
(cause physiological stress, toxicological harm and starvation)

Harmful toxic effects
(plastics can contain many chemicals, some of which are hazardous)

Damage coral reefs
(deprive of oxygen and light, physical damage and increase risk of diseases)

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Based on UNEP 2021. Drowning in plastics

W2&W3

FISHERIES CONTRIBUTION TO MARINE LITTER

ROPES

significant source of microplastics (the older the rope the more microplastics released)

PAINT

paints and antifoulants contain toxic additives and release microplastics

A dark blue icon of a fishing hook and a net with fish inside, positioned on the left side of the water surface.

LOST FISHING GEAR

lines, traps, nets lost by fishing activities into the sea

GARBAGE

produced on board and thrown overboard

LITTER FROM FISHERIES

LITTER PRODUCED ON BOARD

Litter produced on board

Litter produced on board

How long does it take to degrade?

NAPKINS
2-4 weeks

COTTON SHIRT
2-5 months

WOOL GLOVES
1 year

WOOL SOCKS
1-5 years

CIGARETTE BUTS
2-14 years

ALUMINIUM CAN
200 years

GLASS BOTTLES
undetermined

FOAM BUOY
50 years

BUOY FROM
FISHING GEAR
80 years

HOOK
600 years

NYLON LINE
650 years

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Indicative numbers from different sources:
Safet4Sea; SRAM; Joly & Coulis, 2018; Futurism

PASSIVELY FISHED WASTE

Marine litter caught in fishing nets

1. Destroys fishing gear
2. Destroys the catch
3. Fishers lose time

€61.7 million/year
 Economic loss caused by marine litter to the EU fishing fleet

Marine litter caught in fishing nets

Economic impacts on the fishing sector

- Floating plastic debris can **affect the engine** cooling systems and become entangled in propellers
(Takehama, 1990; McIlgorm et al., 2011)
- Litter caught in fishing gears can be responsible for **damaging fishing gears, contaminating catch**, and even **damaging fishing vessels**
(Thomson *et al.*, 2004; Andrady, 2011)
- The total economic cost of this impact has been estimated to be nearly **€61.7** million in the European Union alone
(Mouat *et al.*, 2010; Acoleyen, 2014)
- The costs of removing litter from fishing nets, damage to catches, repairing gear, entangled propellers and obstructed cooling systems account between **1% and 5%** of fishers' revenue
(FAO, 2018)

LOST FISHING GEAR

Lost fishing gear

Abandoned, lost, or otherwise discarded fishing gear (ALDFG)

- ALDFG represent about **10%** of the plastic waste volume present in the oceans
(IUCN, 2021)
- That means somewhere between **500,000** and **1 million tonnes** of fishing gear gets left in the ocean every year
(WWF, 2020)
- Fisheries-related debris is the **largest single category** by volume found in beach litter
(UNEP, 2021)
- ALDFG can continue fishing for years (“ghost fishing”) with high impacts on marine ecosystems and consequently on fish stocks. Ghost gear is the **most deadly** form of marine plastic debris
(WWF, 2020)
- EU estimates that about **20%** of the fishing gear used in Europe is dispersed in the Mediterranean Sea, approximately **11,000 tons**
(INTEMARES, 2023)

ALDFG ecological and socioeconomic impacts

<p>Microplastics Plastic components of derelict gear break down into microplastic pieces, polluting the ocean</p>			
<p>Reduced Use Value of Coastal Areas Derelict gear can end up in nearshore habitats, reducing socioeconomic values of recreation, tourism, education and research, and negatively impacting residential and commercial use</p>			

GHOST FISHING CYCLE

Adapted from www.bluetubebeach.org/blog/ghost-fishing/

OLIVE RIDLEY PROJECT

GHOST FISHING EXAMPLES

Projeto Tamar Brazil/Marine Photobank/Courtesy of World Animal Protection

© Emma Hedley

© Shutterstock / Ian Dyball

© Brian J. Skerry - National Geographic Stock

© Shutterstock / VisionDive / WWF-Sweden

Causes of lost fishing gear

Direct causes

- Poor weather conditions
- Gear entangled on bottom (rocks)
- Conflict with fishing gear
- Shipwrecks and other artificial wrecks
- Vessel conflict with gear

Indirect causes

- Lack of disposal facilities
- Inaccessibility to disposal facilities
- Differentiated disposal facilities (oils, recycling)
- Expenses of disposal facilities

Adapted from [World Animal Protection](#) (accessed Nov. 2023) and UNEP, 2021

Lost fishing gear

NetTag project results (2019)

- **Fishing gear more frequently lost:** traps and small pieces of nets
- **Reasons for losing gear:** type of bottom, shipwrecks, adverse weather conditions, bad handling of the gear or interactions with other fishing gear
- **Hotspots for ALDFG:** fishing areas characterised by irregular bottoms (such as rocky bottoms, reefs, wrecks) or high hydrodynamic areas, up to 5-6 NM from the coast
- **Costs of retrieving lost gear:** a trawler vessel can spend between 5000€ to 12000€
- **Financial incentives to recycle fishing gear:** different national/local programs (not well-known by all fishers)

ALDFG reporting and retrieval

Why is important?

- When gear is lost it can often be retrieved if its location is known
- Understanding the extent, locations and causes of gear loss is key to developing effective prevention and mitigation strategies
- The **retrieval of lost gear is the only way to eliminate its negative impacts** (related to navigational safety, habitat or wildlife damage)
- For certain fishing gear like gillnets, prompt retrieval is most effective (delayed retrieval may lead to a loss of structural integrity, reduced fishing capacity, and is less effective in mitigating negative impacts)
- In case of traps and pots, delayed retrievals (conducted days or weeks after loss) can still effectively mitigate significant negative impacts on species

ALDFG | Gillnets

GILLNETS

- Gillnets are passive fishing gear, work as a "wall" resting in the water, catching fish that get gilled or entangled
- Highly susceptible to getting lost, often neglected due to its affordability and ease of replacement
- Continues catching fish after being lost, impacting the seabed even as it loses buoyancy
- Recommendations: Implement gear marking, explore alternative materials, and incentivise recovery efforts to minimise its environmental impact

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

Funded by
the European Union

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

ALDFG | Pots & Traps

POTS & TRAPS

- When lost, pots and traps continue attracting animals due to the lingering bait, creating a feedback loop with scavengers preying on trapped animals
- As this fishing gear is usually tied with a buoy, entanglements can still happen after traps/pots are destroyed
- Some countries enforce guidelines or regulations, making it mandatory to implement tracking mechanisms (gear marking or GPS) of devices

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

ALDFG | Fish Aggregation Devices

FADs

- Often constructed with netting from old purse seines, posing entanglement risks for fish and other animals around the FADs as well as predators that are attracted to the aggregations of prey species
- While many drifting FADs are tracked using satellite buoys, it is common practice to cease tracking drifting FADs, rather than recovering them, when they drift out of fishing areas
- When lost: continued entanglement of vulnerable species in FAD netting and rafts; and harmful impacts to marine and nearshore habitats of beached FADs

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5
		Anchored		Drifting

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

ALDFG | Hooks & Lines

HOOKS & LINES

- Often discarded when damaged, as they can be quite cheap
- Longlines can span lengthy distances, but their impact when lost is less than other fishing gear, especially if deployed away from the surface
- However, baited hooks continue to catch fish, creating a feedback loop with larger predators preying on baited fish
- Mainline ropes attached to hooks are made from plastic-derived materials, posing entanglement risks to birds if close to the surface
- Curled turtle-safe hooks help mitigate sea turtle entrapment, reducing this specific impact

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Handline Longline

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

ALDFG | Trawl nets

TRAWL NETS

- Expensive and fishers try to avoid losing them
- Often equipped with marking devices for tracking if lost, but entire net loss, necessary for tracking, is rare
- Near seabed trawling, especially in rocky areas, can lead to partial net loss, sinking and moving on the seabed
- Crumpled trawl netting on the seabed has limited chances of catching more fish but may entangle other species like crabs and affect the seabed through smothering
- Surface trawls, usually of polypropylene, can float if torn without weights or catch, having negative impacts similar to FADs

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Mid-water Bottom

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Mid-water Bottom

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

ALDFG | Purse seine nets

PURSE SEINE NETS

WWF 2020. Ghost Gear Report

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- Segments of nets might unintentionally be lost if left on the working deck -> Dedicated containers for repair sections mitigate this risk
- Large segments of purse seine nets can cause similar harm on the sea surface as FADs and floating trawl segments
- Loss of entire nets is rare and intensive recovery efforts are made for lost nets due to their high economic value and replacement cost
- Lost weighted fishing nets likely sink to the seabed, posing entanglement risks for other animals if mesh size is small
- At the seabed, these nets may impact biodiversity or be moved around by bottom currents once the contained catch is degraded

Likelihood of loss

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

Impact once lost

VERY LOW	LOW	MEDIUM	HIGH	VERY HIGH
1	2	3	4	5

GGG, 2021. Best practice framework for management of fishing gear

BYCATCH

Bycatch

- Bycatch encompasses **unintentional captures** during fishing operations, extending beyond target species
- **Trawl, longline, and gillnet** have the highest bycatch rates
- **Major threat to marine vulnerable species:** sea turtles, seabirds, elasmobranchs, marine mammals, corals, and sponges
- Also impact fisheries' profitability and sustainability

Bycatch of Marine Megafauna

- Marine megafauna (seabirds, turtles, cetaceans and elasmobranchs): characterized by longevity, slow growth, low fecundity, delayed sexual maturity, and extensive mobility.
- Bycatch is the leading cause of human-induced mortality in marine megafauna.
- These traits make them particularly sensitive to added mortality, often compromising population viability.

REDUCE project: Reducing the bycatch of threatened megafauna in the East Central Atlantic Ocean

Working area and fishing fleets

INDUSTRIAL PELAGIC FISHERIES (PURSE SEINE, LONGLINE AND TRAWLER FISHERIES)
LONG-DISTANCE EUROPEAN FISHERIES

Purse seine

Longline

Trawler

Designed by David March

REDUCE project aims to gather the efforts of all sectors involved in bycatch to REDUCE bycatch of Marine Megafauna in East Central Atlantic

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union

REDUCING THE BYCATCH OF THREATENED MEGAFaUNA IN THE EAST CENTRAL ATLANTIC OCEAN

Grant Agreement ID 101135583

€ 8.156.593,75 EU Contribution

JAN 2024 - DEC 2027

Funded under Food, Bioeconomy Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment

COORDINATED BY

PARTNERS

ASSOCIATED PARTNERS

Seabirds

- Seabirds are at risk of entanglement in various fishing gears, including longlines, trawls, and nets
- An estimated 200,000 seabirds suffer accidental fatalities annually in Europe due to interactions with fishing gear
- Seabirds, attracted to bait used by anglers, often fall victim to hooks and entanglement in fishing lines
- Diverse feeding habits, including surface and deep diving, increase the vulnerability of seabirds to fishing gear interactions

BirdLife International; NOAA

How bycatch occurs

BirdLife International: https://youtu.be/0_a3oXbfsXo

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Making fisheries safe for seabirds

BirdLife International: https://youtu.be/YGK_1xAZiWQ

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Gillnet bycatch minimisation measures:

- **'Scary bird device'**: Simulates a predator (eagle or falcon) driving birds away from the area of the fishing operation
- **Night settings**: When seabird activity is reduced
- Proper net cleaning and disposal of discards outside of fishing periods: Minimise attraction to birds
- Increased net visibility: Add high-visibility mesh to the top of the net or LED lights
- Increased net depth

Longline bycatch minimisation measures:

- **'Scary bird device'**: Simulates a predator (eagle or falcon) presence to deter birds
- **'Bird scaring lines' or tori lines**: Colourful streamers, to deter birds from the stern of the vessel
- Setting of nets/lines at night: To avoid peak seabird feeding times
- Weighted Lines: To increase baited hooks' sink rate, reducing bird snag risk

Trawl bycatch minimisation measures:

- **Tori lines**
- Night settings

Making fisheries safe for seabirds

- Examples of bird-scaring lines or tori lines

Video: <https://vimeo.com/709031744>

Video: <https://youtu.be/szNQpQzETK4?feature=shared>

Sea turtles

- Sea turtles have survived for more than 200 million years
- There are 7 recognised species in the world
- In Europe, turtles are primarily found in the Mediterranean Sea
- Turtles are **migratory** species; they take **20-30 years to mature** and can **live longer than 100 years**
- Turtles have an important role in the ecosystems maintenance and reflect marine environmental health
- 6 out of the 7 are listed as vulnerable, endangered, or critically endangered on the IUCN Red List

-> Nesting populations in the Mediterranean

-> Largest species of turtle
-> Occasional visitor of the Mediterranean and NE Atlantic

Source: [WISE MARINE](#); [MEDASSET](#); [WWF 2022](#).

Sea turtles

- Bycatch poses a significant threat to all species of marine turtles globally, leading to hundreds of thousands of deaths annually
- Turtles are **air-breathers** and can drown if submerged for long, as it can happen when captured by trawl or set nets
- Turtles incidentally captured by longlines are usually released alive, but many will die, mainly for the ingested line
- Simple **onboard best practices** that can reduce the high mortality of captured turtles:
 - Keep any turtle apparently dead or very weak on the deck until they become active again
 - Cut the line very close to the mouth

Source: [EuroTurtles](#); [WWF 2022](#).

Making fisheries safe for sea turtles

Turtle Excluder Device (TED)

- a grid which diverts marine turtles and other large marine fauna out of a trawl net, already used in tropical shrimp trawls

Source: [WWF 2022](#).

Video: <https://youtu.be/jyhumLE7B40>

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Sharks

Adapted from: Artwork by Jamy Silver © Save Our Seas Foundation

WHY ARE SHARKS IMPORTANT?

Across the world's oceans, there are over **500 species** of shark.

Whale shark

Goblin shark

They have inhabited our oceans for over **400 million years.**

Basking shark

Zebra shark

Tiger shark

Angel shark

Catshark

Scalloped hammerhead

Blue shark

Bonnethead

Epaulette shark

Some are **top predators**, others are the **clean-up crew** of the ocean.

Their diverse roles are part of a balance needed for **healthy oceans.**

Sharks

Adapted from: Artwork by Jamy Silver © Save Our Seas Foundation

WHY ARE SHARKS IMPORTANT?

Losing sharks can disrupt the **delicate ecosystem balance** that they help maintain.

As many as **100 million** sharks may be killed every year in commercial fisheries.

Many shark populations have **declined by more than 90%**, due to overfishing, climate change and habitat loss.

Our future depends the oceans.

The ripple effects of an ocean without sharks are complex and potentially devastating.

Marine mammals

- Marine mammals play crucial ecological roles and are indicators of marine ecosystem health
- They are generally **highly mobile**, possess **large body sizes**, and have **low reproductive rates**
- Which makes them **vulnerable** to human-related stressors
- The disappearance of large predators (e.g. dolphins) has a wider impact on the environment and marine resources
- Bycatch/entanglement in fishing gear poses the **greatest threat** to marine mammal species globally
- Although it's **illegal** to catch marine mammals
- Over 600,000 marine mammals are accidentally captured each year worldwide

BOTTLENOSE DOLPHIN

LONG-FINNED PILOT WHALE

GRAY SEAL

Source: [FAO](#); [CETAMBICION project](#)

Marine mammals

Why bycatch happens?

- Same fishing area or target species (trophic competition)
- Attracting dolphins near fishing boats (depredation)
- Lack of visibility/selectivity of some fishing gear that accidentally catches non-target animals

Source: [CETAMBICION project](#)

Marine mammals bycatch mitigation

- Improving the visibility of fishing gear
 - ✓ Active or passive acoustic deterrents
 - ✓ Acoustic reflectors
 - ✓ Informative warning signal (DOLPHINFREE project)
 - ✓ Change of net colour
 - ✓ Lighting of nets
- Modification of fishing gear
 - ✓ Modification of the nets
 - ✓ Trawl exclusion system
 - ✓ "Intelligent" fishing gear
- Changes in fishing practices
 - ✓ Alternative fishing gear
 - ✓ Duration and period of immersion of the fishing gear
 - ✓ Depth of the net (2-4m below surface)
 - ✓ Adoption of good practice
- Fishing effort limitation and management
 - ✓ Time and space closure
 - ✓ Area closure based on reaching a catch limit
 - ✓ "Move-on" rule
 - ✓ Predictive fisheries management
- Regulatory and incentive measures
 - ✓ Regulation, Monitoring and surveillance
 - ✓ Economic levers

Source: [CETAMBICION project](#)

Acoustic Deterrent Devices - 'pingers'

Excluder Device

Backdown procedure

FISHING GEAR INNOVATIONS DESIGNED TO LOWER THE RISK OF ENTANGLEMENT FOR LARGE WHALES

Adapted from whale illustrations
© Parks Canada

DEPLOY FISHING GEAR MADE OF COMPONENTS WITH A LOW BREAKING STRENGTH

The use of polyethylene, time-tension line cutters or plastic links, for example, offers a breaking strength of 770 kg or less, which makes it easier to release an entangled animal

USE A MAXIMUM ROPE DIAMETER OF 16 mm

Too large a diameter increases the breaking strength and complicates the release of an entangled animal, while excessively thin rope (6 mm) can lead to more severe skin injuries

USE ROPELESS GEAR

Technologies include various types of remote triggering devices and GPS positioning and recovery systems in order to eliminate the need for vertical lines

REDUCE FLOATING ROPE ON WATER SURFACE

Adopt good fishing practices to reduce floating rope such as rope shot, Inflatable lift bag or simply properly coiling one's rope

USE SINKING ROPE BETWEEN TRAPS OR POTS

Sinking rope helps limit the amount of rope floating above the seafloor

AVOID USING SINGLE-POT GEAR

Traps or pots can be deployed in series to reduce the number of buoys and the amount of rope used

Safe handling and release

- Maximises survival chances of bycatch species after interaction with fishing gear
- Includes best practice methods and vessel manoeuvres to avoid taking bycatch species
- In purse seine operations, bycatch can be released from the net whilst in the water or released once brought on deck
- With line fishing operations bycatch may either be released from the side of the vessel or after being brought on board
- There are safe handling and release guides for different species and fishing gear

Source: [BMIS](#)

ACTIONS TO REDUCE PLASTIC POLLUTION FROM FISHERIES

Tackling sea-based marine litter sources

EU actions

- **EU Directive** 2019/883 on **port reception facilities** to tackle sea-based marine litter
- **EU Directive** 2019/904 on **single use plastic** products and **fishing gear** containing plastic
- One of the six main interim targets of the **Zero Pollution Action Plan** for 2030 is **reducing litter at sea by 50%**
- Council Regulation (EC) No 1224/2009 requires Union fishing vessels to have the equipment on board to **retrieve lost gear**

Directive 2019/883 on Port Reception Facilities

EU Directive for the delivery of waste from ships

- Aims to protect the marine environment by reducing discharges of waste from ships, and to improve efficiency of maritime operations in ports; ensuring that more waste is delivered on shore, in particular garbage, including waste from the fishing sector such as derelict fishing gear
- **100% INDIRECT FEE OBLIGATION** – allows the **FREE delivery of all litter** (including fishing gears and passively fished litter), up to the maximum dedicated storage capacity of the boat
- **GREEN-SHIP rebate** - fishing vessels should be encouraged to undertake certain measures (waste prevention and on-board waste management) to be eligible for a green-ship rebate

Potential use of eco-friendly materials

Preventing plastic from ending up in the ocean in the first place!

- Current development of **biodegradable nets and line** -> reducing ghost fishing and microplastics
- Maintaining strength and durability for a few months and degrades in water

<https://www.4ocean.com/pages/sustainable-fishing>

<https://www.britannica.com/explore/savingearth/commercial-fishing>

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Tackling sea-based marine litter sources

Fishers are part of the solution!

- Delivery of waste to port reception facilities, including fishing gear waste
- Collecting and bringing passively fished waste ashore
- Retrieving or reporting lost fishing gear
- Recycling end-of-life fishing gear
- Participation on Clean-up Initiatives; Fishing for Litter

© NetTag project. Clean Ocean Day

Tackling sea-based marine litter sources

Fishers are part of the solution!

agenda-docapesca.weebly.com/noticias/a-pesca-por-um-mar-sem-lixo-na-ilha-da-culatra-e-em-aveiro

- All fishers have a bag or trash bin on board
- All boats have space on board to bring the waste produced back to land

How to reduce plastic waste?

Individual actions

use your own bottle

avoid unnecessary packaging

opt for fully recyclable packaging

bring your own lunch box

dispose of plastic recycling correctly

pick up litter & participate in beach clean-ups

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Based on [EUFIC](#) and [Safety4Sea](#)

ENERGY TRANSITION IN THE FISHERIES SECTOR

Ocean & Climate crisis

The ocean acts as the

PLANET'S "LUNGS"

and a massive

CARBON SINK

BLUE CARBON ECOSYSTEMS

Seagrass meadows, kelp forests, tidal marshes, and seabed sediments **store significant amounts of CO₂**

FISH

Contribute to the global carbon cycle by moving carbon from the surface to deeper waters

Adapted from OCEANA 2023. [Fighting the climate crisis requires climate-smart shing in Europe](#)

Fisheries & Climate change

6
M. TONS OF CO₂
PER YEAR DUE TO
FUEL BURNING

1 DIRECT CO₂ EMISSIONS

Most EU fleets are **fossil fuel dependent and inefficient**, and not resilient to shocks in energy prices.

Certain fishing methods, such as **bottom trawling**, consume more fuel than others

2 REMOVAL OF FISH BIOMASS

Overfishing in the EU has led to many **fish populations being below sustainable levels**, likely disturbing their role in the ecosystem and carbon cycle

↓ CO₂ STORAGE
CAPACITY OF THE OCEAN
DUE TO OVERFISHING

3 DISTURBANCE TO VULNERABLE BLUE CARBON HABITATS

High-impact bottom fishing methods can **disturb sensitive habitats**, releasing carbon back into the water.

This released carbon can then be converted to CO₂, potentially increasing ocean acidification and reducing the ocean's capacity to absorb atmospheric CO₂

↑ CO₂ RELEASE
FROM BLUE CARBON
HABITATS DUE TO
DAMAGING PRACTICES

Greenhouse gases (GHG)

What are GHG and how do fisheries contribute to them?

- Human activities, including fisheries, produce GHG through the consumption fossil fuel
- GHG is a group of gases contributing to global warming and climate change (carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide and fluorinated gases)
- GHG trap heat from the sun to keep surface warm while some heat is released back into space

[NOAA](#)

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<https://climatekids.nasa.gov/greenhouse-effect/>

GHG effects on the ocean

1. Ocean acidification

- shelled organisms (e.g. oysters, clams, sea urchins) have difficulties building and maintaining shells
- jeopardises this food source and the larger food web

2. Sea level rise

- as the ocean warms, the volume of water increases
- coasts at risk from erosion and high-tide flooding

3. Warmer temperatures melting sea ice

(contributing to sea level rise)

- glaciers are shrinking
- the Arctic is warming most rapidly compared to global average

[NOAA 2021](#)

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Net Zero emissions by 2050

Fisheries and aquaculture sectors

- Under the Green Deal, Europe has committed to become the first **climate-neutral** continent **by 2050** and to **cut the GHG emissions by at least 55% by 2030** (compared to 1990)
- This means a **reduction of 30% by 2030** (compared to 2005) in the **fishing sector**
- To reach a neutral CO₂ footprint, all sectors must play their part in **emitting less** and **protecting natural ecosystems**, such as the ocean, so they absorb more carbon
- The European Commission proposed **measures to accelerate energy transition**, focusing on fuel efficiency and renewable, low-carbon power sources (COM(2023) 100 final)

[EC, 2023](#); [OCEANA, 2023](#)

Climate-smart management requirements

Cut fossil fuel emissions

FUEL SAVINGS

50%

can be achieved by optimising fishing vessel structures, gears, and routes

100%

from switching to renewable energy fuels & propulsion

The EU's energy transition initiative of its fisheries must transform the sector to one of low-impact

Prioritise moving away from the most **fuel-intensive and high impact fishing** – such as bottom trawling – towards:

Fuel efficient practices

Selective, low-impact gears

Green energy sources

Climate-smart management requirements

Rebuild and maintain fish biomass

This approach has **multiple benefits:**

- 1** Protect the role of fish in the carbon cycle
- 2** More fish abundance reduces fuel & operational costs
- 3** Decreases fleet's fuel footprint per kg of seafood

Strategies to reduce GHG emissions

- Fuel loads per catch can range based on gear, vessel, catch, and more
 - Slowing down during steaming (reduce fuel use whenever possible)
 - Investing in technological innovations for vessels
 - Remaining adaptable and resilient as the industry evolves

EPRS, 2023. [Decarbonising the fishing sector](#)

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<https://business.esa.int/projects/showcases/electronic-record-keeping-system-for-commercial-fishermen>

<https://www.mywestshore.com/great-commercial-fishing-boat/>

Let's clean up the ocean together!

Thank you for your attention

www.nettagplus.eu

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